

(In)Visibility Matters in Clinical and Translational Medicine

Barbara Hendriks, Cornelia Schendzielorz and Martin Reinhart

Abstract

Science is confronted with a plethora of expectations how scientific knowledge impacts society. These expectations are commonly formulated in science policy concepts, such as “basic research”, “science in and for society”, “applied research and development for exploitation”, “responsible research and innovation”. Against this background our contribution deals with two such influential scientific concepts in the biomedical context – innovation and translation – and explores how they relate to each other. We analyzed interviews with clinician scientists and their collaborators in research and clinic that were conducted in a two-year evaluation of the BIH Charité (Junior) Clinician Scientist program providing an exemplary case for innovation in medical specialist training. Moreover, it is the largest translational research training program for physicians in Germany, which is also among the largest in Europe. Our empirical study shows that the concept of translation balances visibility and invisibility in research and clinical practice to enable and ensure qualitative novelty and to optimize innovation processes, without having to subordinate itself entirely to the pressure of economization.

Keywords

translational medicine, science policy, medical professions, valuation studies

Introduction: Which concept for health futures?

Imagining alternative health futures needs concepts – preferably novel concepts – that capture ambitions and expectations of practitioners and researchers alike. The policy discourse provides plenty of such concepts such as translation and innovation. For these concepts to materialize in actual health care it requires practitioners such as broadly trained physicians with sound

knowledge in clinical practice as well as in medical research to make sense of them and incorporate them in their work practices. Innovation is a well-established umbrella-term describing the development of something new, be it through incremental progress of research and knowledge production through creative destruction (Schumpeter 1934) or through groundbreaking knowledge gain and scientific revolutions (Kuhn 1996). It has been subject to versatile descriptions of innovation as linear phases or feedback models from idea development to market launch or knowledge transfer (Etzkowitz and Leydesdorff 2000, Owen et al 2012, Flink and Kaldewey 2018a, 2018, Blümel et al. 2016, Blümel et al. 2015). While innovation provides a narrative that is economically oriented and linked to an output and investment logic, the concept of translation provides a counter-narrative, which has emerged in medicine with a stronger orientation towards the common good. In contrast to innovation, the more recent notion of translation is not yet mapped comprehensively and is still very much “in the making”. The meaning of translation as a term thus remains quite vague as it is often described, grasped and conceived as a translational process between different fields, areas or entities where something is implemented, transformed, transferred etc. (Mittra and Milne 2013; Kraft 2013; Butler 2008; Cambrosio 2006; Blümel et al. 2015; Blümel 2018; Krueger et al. 2019).

This paper investigates how political concepts reshape action in (bio)medicine and what the effects are for medical practice in general. For this purpose, we investigate (in)visible translation practices in the context of university medicine. Our insights are based on an empirical evaluation study of the *BIH Charité (Junior) Clinician Scientist Program ((J)CSP)* that we conducted from 2019 until 2021. This is an appropriate place to observe the relationship between innovation and translation, since the program itself introduces an innovation in the formation of medical specialists while simultaneously addressing the institutional challenge of implementing translation. In that regard, more solidified concepts such as innovation are then challenged at the practical level. We focus on the professional work context of clinician

scientists at the *BIH Charité (Junior) Clinician Scientist Program* that is to be located at the crossroads of bio-medical research and clinical patient care as a societal care service. In the wake of the perennial accompanying qualitative study the question of visibility respectively invisibility and to some extent related question of valuation emerged as helpful analytical categories in order to decipher the intricate relation of translation and innovation. Tracing the arrangements and orders of visibility, invisibility and valuation in the hybrid professional work context of clinician scientists, allows us to reconstruct how translation and innovation are interrelated in the daily working practices of clinician scientists in translational (bio)medicine. We thereby scrutinize key assumptions underpinning the translational turn, as translation is often oversimplified and presented as improving health care systems without negative consequences or side-effects. Pinpointing which working practices are (in)visible in translational medicine, we work out how visibility and invisibility relate to valuation, recognition and control of these working practices. We then conclude on how (in)visibilities and (de)valuations feed back into the framing of concepts of translation and innovation in translational research and medicine.

In order to investigate how policy concepts are used as powerful tools to order and impact professional working practices in translational (bio)medicine, we refer to the sociology of (e)valuation as a theoretical framework to relate the valorization of biomedical work to the visibility or invisibility of that work. This approach enables us to capture how policy concepts are used as powerful tools to manage visibilities to change valuations in the biomedical field. We, thereby follow existing STS studies that critically question (politically) accepted concepts and their modes of action in the context of (bio)medicine (Prainsack 2018; 2014; Dickenson 2016).

In chapter 2, we start by explaining the paradoxical relationship between translation and commodification in health care. We then present the concepts of (in)visibility and (de)valuation

serving to analyze the empirical data and elaborate how they are related in the context of translational research and medicine in an economized health care system. In chapter four, we outline our methods and data of the empirical study. In chapter five, we present our empirical findings. From these results, we draw in chapter six more generalized conclusions on the asymmetries of (in)visibility and valuation as we encountered a paradoxical relationship between visibility and (e)valuation that affects first, the relationship between innovation and translation and second, the understanding of the current health care system. In chapter seven, we theorize on the interrelations of concepts between political discourse and professional practice of clinician scientists and reflect on the paradoxical dynamics of (in)visibilities, (de)valuation and commodification in translational research and medicine. In our final chapter, we draw conclusions on how science policy concepts intrude the reality of science.

The translational turn in (bio)medicine: an accelerator of commodification in health care?

A "translational turn" (Kraft 2013) in (bio)medicine has been evident for at least a decade, entailing a critical look at the relationship between the laboratory and the medical treatment in the clinic, prompting to reconsider the role of innovation in health care. It has since become clear that there is not one consistent concept of translational research, but different models, understandings and meanings of translational research and processes coexist. "Ask ten people what translational research means and you're likely to get ten different answers" (Butler 2008). Translation is conceptualized in different forms, e.g. as a linear innovation process, divided into various phases of research and development; as an innovation gap represented by the "valley of death" (Butler 2008) or as overlapping concentric circles (see Pettibone et al. 2018). With these conceptions various expectations and drivers are linked (Mittra and Milne 2013), which shape the meaning of translation in individual situations. However, as a common denominator, translation can be conceived as the process that attempts to bridge the gap between research

(basic or clinical) and clinical application, which is commonly known as “from bench to bedside and back”.

Despite being so vague in its definition, translation is not only being put into practice, but it has also become a central science policy agenda. The vagueness may have helped in applying the concept in a flexible manner, however, preventing the institution of any standard evaluation criteria for successful translation. The meaningfulness of translation is no longer questioned because translation has manifested itself as a normatively valuable concept. Consequently, it is not possible for practicing biomedical researchers to reject translation in their work environment. Robinson (2019) calls this state a "translational mode of knowledge" in which all biomedical research becomes either potentially translatable or is seen as pre-translational (Robinson 2019, 98). We thus went from a “translational turn” (Kraft 2013) to a “translational mode of knowledge” (Robinson 2019) with the consequence that translation has evolved from an approach to improve medical research and practice to a paradigmatic norm, without an ideal translational standard having emerged in practice (e.g. quantitative indicators or other evaluation criteria). Translation has developed into a guiding framework for action that can hardly be critically questioned. We argue that translation becomes even more powerful in its scope when the dynamics of commodification are placed at the center of reflection.

The power of translation becomes visible when one takes a closer look at institutionalized translational practices such as clinician scientist programs, which are designed to link research back to clinical work at the level of practicing actors. The successful integration of research into the clinic represents a major science policy concern. Decentralized clinician scientist programs are being established worldwide in university hospitals in order to overcome a domination of clinical practice and care and to integrate research more fruitfully in the clinic (de Groot et al. 2020; Vignola-Gagné 2014; Wilson-Kovacs and Hauskeller 2012). Although there are places and situations, in which clinic and research are combined successfully,

translational work is not the common standard in current university medicine. Furthermore, the structural conditions are such that a connection between research and clinic leads to frictions in the work of practitioners. In Germany, clinician scientist programs offer clinically active physicians a special amount of payed working time in order to practice research. The amount of research time, however, depends on the program and the level of clinical education (year of residency), but usually comprises between 20% and 50% of the overall working time.

Due to commodification and financialization of health care, which is accompanied by scarcity of human resources, clinician scientists still prioritize patient care and health over research in daily practice. Subsequently, clinician scientists' research resources resulting from their guaranteed protected research time is partially spent on patient care. Our previous survey of the BIH Charité (Junior) Clinician Scientist Program as part of the multi-method evaluation study shows that only 50% of clinician scientists manage to comply with their protected research time. In that program, fellows are usually guaranteed 20% to 50% of protected research time up to three years of their fellowship. The reason given by the respondents for not using the whole amount is that patient care takes more time (Hendriks et al. 2021, 31). The expenditure of research resources for patient treatment seems understandable from an ethical as well as a professional medical perspective: Clinician scientists are educated and trained as physicians and their professional role thus is focused on patient welfare. In short and ethical terms, the higher valuation of patient treatment is reasonable; however, in a long-term view it reproduces the disparity between research and patient care, retarding translation as well as innovation in medicine, and thus hindering the patient welfare in the long-run. Long-term perspectives, such as the development of drugs and active substances, which require a lot of research and development time, are pushed into the background of acute treatment settings or is left to private pharmaceutical companies. Prioritization of patient treatment might challenge the altruistic model of "we medicine" (Dickenson 2016) – a one size fits all medicine for all. It promotes the

privatization of health care instead of improving public health as part of the common good. At this point, it is necessary to critically examine the ‘politics of translation’, which we attempt to do below.

Processes of expanding global and local economization and commodification of health care are of major interest for STS (Çalışkan and Callon 2009; 2010; Rose 2007; van Hoyweghen 2007, Etzkowitz and Leydesdorff 2000; Kleinman et al. 2001). In this context, questions arise about effective policies to develop high-quality health care systems that are accessible to all (Mackintosh and Koivusalo 2005). The concept of translation represents such a novel policy measure. However, paradoxically, the emergence of translation as an active counterpart of innovation may be interpreted as the result of a solution attempt oriented to a market logic, since the need for innovation in scientific practices in the field of (bio-)medicine is justified by economic exploitation and valorization imperatives: a lack of "return on investments" and the need to overcome "innovation gaps" are key drivers for translation (Kraft 2013). Translation as a concept is thus a solution strategy for optimizing the healthcare sector that has already been adapted to a market logic. This raises questions for further STS engagements of whether translation exacerbates commodification and neoliberalization (Berman 2014) of health care or acts as a trojan horse, integrating new practices in university medicine that undermine market principles with the aim of (re)synergising research with the clinic (Robinson 2019).

Relating visibility and valuation in translational research and medicine

When it comes to making specific modes of action and powers in (bio)medicine visible, it is significant not only to examine the mechanisms that are readily visible, but also to turn to the mechanisms that are more hidden (the ‘hinterland’). The theoretical concept of visibility allows us to draw attention towards (in)visible social mechanisms in university (bio)medicine and link them to forms of (e)valuation to make rather invisible power relations visible. Based on Brighenti’s conception, we understand visibility as the complex field where the visible and the

articulable coexist (Brighenti 2007; 2017). The invisible is no less operative and thus no less powerful than the visible, but the invisible is without a theme (Brighenti 2017). In daily work a theme can be a (structural) working problem, e.g. indignation or frustration about working conditions. Giving invisible working practices a theme to make them visible thus is one way to make them potentially valuable since they can be addressed, counted and evaluated. Since the visible and the valuable are so closely intertwined, asymmetries and distortions of visibility are the norm (Brighenti 2007, 326). For science visibility comes in at least two forms: epistemic and social (Reinhart 2021: 6). “First, scientific cultures are in central epistemic aspects primarily visible cultures. Ideals of objectivity and research practices [...] centre around focusing scientific attention on obscure or as-yet invisible aspects of the world and convincing others of their factualness by making them visible (Daston 2000; Daston and Galison 2007) [...]. Second, scientific cultures are in central social aspects visible cultures, because reputation plays a paramount role in assigning status and truthfulness to individual researchers and institutions (Shapin 1994)” (Reinhart 2021: 6f). That holds also true for the medical field. But what about the visibility of research in the clinic? Despite these forms of scientific visibility and their potential to generate attention we noticed within our field investigation that in university hospitals clinical work is highly visible and research is more likely to be less visible or even invisible. Indeed, a dominance of patient care is useful in emergency and surgical settings and can be considered functional. However, in medical areas where research is a central part of medical practice and care, such permanent and hence dominant visibility of clinic has to be questioned, because visibility is directly linked to recognition (Brighenti 2007, 329).¹ In view of this, a visible clinic is and (presumably) stays more recognized and powerful than invisible research.

¹ We conceive recognition as a form of social visibility with significant consequences on the relationship between social groups, e.g. between minorities and mainstream (ibid.), and as such as a form of symbolic power (Voswinkel 2001, Honneth 2010).

During our field investigation we wondered, what might the reason be for the clinic's visibility? At an administrative level, visibility of patient care is closely linked to managerial reorganization processes in university hospitals. In Germany, flat rates per case have been systematized according to the DRG-classification system due to a change in the legal framework, which has led to an enormous push for financialization within the German health care system (Klein-Hitpaß and Scheller-Kreinsen 2015). Since 2004, flat rates per case have been used to remunerate individually defined medical service complexes with the aim of replacing the cost recovery principle, which has been in place since 1972. The introduction of the DRG effectuates a persistent working time intensification that was accompanied by increasing public criticism concerning the economization of the health care system. This context is noticeable and decisive as the funding and development of a formation program of clinician scientists is a new vehicle to oppose the commodification and financialization of healthcare by implementing institutionalized protected time for research into the clinic. It seeks to counter the concern of a de-academization of university medicine and to fulfill the university hospital's claim to realize the triad of patient care, research and teaching. Clinician scientists who follow a clinician scientist program receive a fixed salary in line with the physician pay scale, but their time for research is funded through public resources, coming for example from the Ministry for Education and Research (BMBF) or the German Research Foundation (DFG). The financial support of clinician scientists is directed towards patient care and research in the same amount. However, the continuous high visibility of patient care leads to unequal distributions of value and value attribution. This steady urgency driven visibility of clinical practice results in a dominance of clinic over research, because (in)visibility besides its linkage to recognition is closely related to (e)valuation (Reinhart, Krüger and Hesselmann 2019; Hesselmann, Schendzielorz and Krüger (2021)). These visibility effects thus have an influence on how the targeted production of (in)visibility and (in)transparency determines what or who is evaluated. Following Brighenti conceiving „recognition and control [...] as two opposing

outcomes of visibility“ (Brighenti 2007, 323), the latter also conditions what or whose work can be controlled and recognized, valued and devalued. In light of the repercussions between visibility and valuation the clinical work enters “a zone of [...] super-visibility [...] a condition of paradoxical double bind that forbids you to do what you are simultaneously required to do [...]” (ibid., 330). In consequence, the demands for clinician scientists are twofold: they must both stand up to the existing super-visibility of the clinic in daily working practices – which is connected to certain arguments and justifications (e.g. the well-being of patients) – and at the same time fight for recognition of research in a clinic-dominated work environment. Appointed to combine both, research and clinic, clinician scientists are caught in a dilemma. Our empirical analysis delves into this dilemma addressing the following questions: How is the (in)visibility of research and clinic shaped in the clinician scientist workspace? What practices are developed by clinician scientists to increase the visibility of translational research in the clinic? By answering these questions, we aim to identify existing *regimes of visibility* as modes of action within translational university medicine and shed light on how they rule and stabilize practices in the health care system.

Methods and Data

To analyze (in)visibility of research and clinical practice in the clinician scientist programs, we use 20 interviews that we conducted during the above-mentioned two-year multi-method evaluation of the BIH Charité (Junior) Clinician Scientist Program from 2019 until 2021. In the qualitative part of the evaluation study, which we draw on for this article, we interviewed clinician scientists, clinic directors, research mentors, and professors who participated within the program (see table 1). It provides its fellows either 20% protected research time for their junior-fellows at the beginning of their residency (first and second year) or 50% of protected time for research for the already clinically experienced fellows (from the third year of

residency). The research portion of paid work time is not counted toward clinical staff quotas. The latter remain unchanged since the research portions are paid from additional public funds. We conducted all interviews face-to-face from November 2019 until March 2020 with the help of a semi-structured interview guide. At the time of the survey, clinical practice and research had not yet been significantly impacted by the Covid-19 pandemic, so we were able to conduct and finalize our fieldwork before first lockdown.

TABLE 1: INTERVIEW RESPONSE PER GROUP

Group invited	Invited	(in %)	Conducted	(in %)
Clinician scientist	26	57,8 %	9	45,0 %
Junior fellows	7	15,6 %	4	20,0 %
Clinic directors and research mentors and professors	12	26,7 %	7	35,0 %
Total	45	100 %	20	100 %

The interview questions for clinician scientists focused on the following guiding themes:

- Motivation of becoming a clinician scientist,
- Protected research time,
- Translational research,
- Collaboration and interdisciplinary work,
- Research infrastructure,
- Career aspiration,
- Compatibility of family and career.

For clinic directors who are involved in patient treatment, but also operating on a management level, we included further themes:

- Measures for the successful integration of clinician scientists into the clinic,
- Opportunities for clinician scientist qualification for patient care and research,
- Marginal utility of clinician scientists in everyday clinical practice,
- Dual demands from research and patient care,
- Measures for the expansion and further development of clinician scientist careers in the context of German university medicine.

The length of interviews varies from 45 minutes to 120 minutes. Interviews with clinic directors tend to be shorter due to their overall limited time and interviews with clinician scientists longer. We recruited the interviewees from different medical fields that we summarized into four medical clusters (see table 2 in appendix) in order to ensure anonymity for the interviewees. We conducted interviews with clinician scientists in all four clusters: conservative, surgical, diagnostic and hybrid. We further interviewed clinic directors and research mentors from the conservative and hybrid clusters. We were eager to recruit clinic directors and research mentors and professors from the other two clusters (surgical and diagnostic) as well, but our interview requests were unfortunately unsuccessful. Especially in the field of surgery the recruitment was difficult due to the overall workload and tightly packed schedule as well as routine-based work processes.

With the consent of the interviewees, the interviews were recorded and subsequently transcribed and pseudonyms were given. We analyzed the interview transcripts “line by line” and inductively with the help of the text analyzing program MAXQDA and the method of quality content analysis by Mayring (2000). The inductive coding method of qualitative content analysis aims to reproduce the content verbalized by the interviewees in condensed form at the level of codes. A total of 1931 text segments were coded in the 20 interview documents and these were assigned higher-level codes in terms of content. Taken together, the codes form the overall coding scheme, represent an abstract picture of the clinician scientist program. The

interview material was coded by two researchers to ensure intercoder-reliability and the results were discussed frequently in joint sessions with three project members.

Empirical Findings

Invisibility and devaluation of research

Research output in medicine is traced and ranked not only epistemically through authorship and numbers of publications but also socially through digital selves (Reinhart 2022: 179ff), i.e. via different indicators: H-Index, third-party funding – just to name a few. Publicly available output and countable byproducts of research hence is visible and assessable. In contrast to general epistemic and social visibility (Reinhart 2022: 179f), it becomes empirically evident in our data that daily laboratory research, which haven't produced a traceable – that means published and/or countable – output yet, is invisible for others in the clinic. A junior clinician scientist illustrates that his research in the clinical context is prone to be devalued by being compared with “watching Netflix all day” by his clinical co-workers. He thereby addresses the invisibility of his research activity for others in the context of the provision of technical equipment in the lab:

“To be honest, when someone is doing a lot of research or is going to do a lot of research and has an old laptop at home, having no battery. And he wants to buy a new – I don't know – a MacBook, then I think 'do it'. I mean these are all people who are doing research and they love doing it. [...] And they do not sit at home and watch Netflix the whole day [...] On the other side: There are people from the industry who look at those people [performing research at the Charité university hospital] and say: 'we offer you consultation, expense accounts, company cars and so on'. I saw people who went into the industry and they earned three times as much. And they had their new MacBook laying on the desk at their first day.” (Junior Clinician Scientist, cluster: diagnostic, male).

This statement exemplifies to what extent research is devalued in the clinic, because it is invisible as a daily practice and routine. In contrast to the university hospital, the pharmaceutical industry is named as a sector, which seems to value research (more) than practitioners in the university clinic, which is among others highlighted by the provisioned new MacBook at the first day of work. In Germany, public financed clinical research and industry research run separately from each other, with the boundary often being ethical in nature. The pharmaceutical industry stands for economically focused healthcare, whereas publicly funded research stands for research "for all". The MacBook as an expensive purchase, which is usually not provided to researchers in the public financed university clinic, stands for recognition.

Clinician scientists are not only confronted with comparisons such as "watching Netflix all day", but also with the fact that their protected research time is termed by clinicians as "leisure time". The verbalization of research as leisure time exemplifies that research is not recognized by all clinicians as working time. It is precisely this context, in which even biomedical research professors working in the clinic devalue laboratory research. We asked a research professor how research-oriented translational education and training in general should be. Instead of addressing the long-term changes and chances brought about by translational research, the interviewee points to the short-term consequences for patient care. His answer addresses the potential suffering of patients due to research-orientated doctors working in the clinic:

"Interviewer: In general, how research oriented should medical education be?"

Participant: Well, that's the other question. So how many patients suffer because research-oriented doctors only have half the clinic time. That would also have to be asked... well that's always a two-sided test, yes? So, you would have to weigh and measure harm and benefit and also consider both to be possible. It is also quite possible that physicians working in research do not have certain skills. And, thus also endanger patient welfare." (Research professor, cluster: hybrid, male).

We find in our data that most of the physicians who exclusively work clinically address clinical treatment in a narrow manner by framing it mostly as emergency situations: patients enter the clinic and have to be treated immediately. The long-term perspective of translational research – seeing that research could help develop new treatments and therapies or identify causes for specific diseases – stays mostly invisible in that urgent clinical context. The reason for that short-sighted view is not grounded in the fact that the interviewed clinicians or researchers do not see the benefit of research for clinical practice in general. On the contrary: biomedical research is perceived as an important part of university medicine, but our data shows that clinical practice absorbs a significant amount of clinic workers resources and this prevents the long-term perspective from being implemented in practice. In the next section, we analyze how it is that research is considered relevant for patient well-being but is difficult to practice in a clinical context. We argue that the reason for that particularly lies in the supervisibility (Brighenti 2007) of clinical practice.

Super-visibility of clinical practice

We find that clinical practice overall is highly visible, accepted and not questioned at all from those we interviewed. Just as research is undervalued in the clinical setting, patient care is highlighted as especially important and justified by the ethical component of the medical profession.

“I often say: To be a good doctor is your primary obligation, because you have responsibility towards these people. And if there are things you are bad at, this could cause dramatic consequences! And if you are bad at something in the clinic, maybe that could have dramatic consequences. Compared to this, the prioritization is clear, I find it less fatal to put an experiment on hold or to risk that the experiment fails”. (Research professor, cluster: conservative, male).

Although, clinician scientists at the BIH Charité (J)CSP have protected time for research the valuation in favor of patient care compared to research is present several times in the interviews. A research professor from the hybrid medical cluster claimed that to favor clinical practice over research can be interpreted as professional obligation and collegiality.

“Interviewer: You just named it `collegiality` when clinician scientists set aside their [protected and payed] research time to help out their colleagues in the clinic. This raises the question for me: is there such a thing as a marginal benefit of that collegiality? How far can you go as a clinician scientist? Assuming you had to regulate it, where would be the limit of that `collegiality`?”

Participant: Well, you have to regulate it. The question is whether the regulation is powerful enough in an emergency, when it comes to patients. Or whether it makes sense. If you're a doctor, you have to ask yourself what you're doing ethically when you say, "I'm free from clinical [obligations] because I'm doing research today" and to see the need in the clinic everyday somehow. (...) The question is simply how the system exploits this. Whether the system speculates on the fact that one has a good character or whether you really take it only in case of emergency”. (Research professor, cluster: hybrid, male).

The professional obligation comprises ethical as well as cooperative aspects and conventions to support each other as colleagues in case of work overload within the university hospital. The question of compliance with protected research time is thus left to the "system" comprising individuals who must esteem and decide if this is disproportionate collegiality or an acute emergency. What is described here as the “system” by the participant may in sociological terms be better described as essential of the medical profession whereas the ethical dimension of being a doctor is institutionalized through the Hippocratic oath (Cavanaugh 2018). In that regard, the reduction of clinical time during residency also becomes an ethical issue, because the implementation of protected research time during the clinician scientist program changes the

amount of clinical experience during residency. In Germany, residency training usually lasts five years. During this time, research is practiced outside of regular working hours. This phenomenon is discussed under the term of “Feierabendforschung [after-work research]” (Dragun et al. 2019)" and it is currently criticized that research – as an important aspect of university medicine – is thereby marginalized, since it is shifted into a space that is largely untraceable and not regulated by German labor policy. Clinician scientist programs represent an attempt to reintegrate research into regular working hours and thus make it more visible. However, the reduction of clinical practice in favor of research is problematized in the context of necessary physician experiential knowledge as this statement exemplifies.

“If you compare now, a clinician in the fourth year of residency or a clinician scientist in the fourth year of training, who has already had two years of 50 percent protected research time. The latter of course cannot have exactly the same clinical experience as a clinician. But I don't think that you necessarily notice that you are less experienced in everyday life, because you can also compensate a lot through knowledge and reading up, for example”. (Clinician Scientist, cluster: hybrid, female).

The lack of clinical time and experience is not only discussed concerning a potential lack of medical skills that is addressed as an ethical as well as a professional concern as the above-mentioned statements illustrate. It further becomes a relevant issue concerning economic and financial factors, which university hospitals in general have to deal with.

“For once the cost pressure in the hospital is just crazy. [...] If you look at the figures in all hospitals at all, then the number of patients continues to rise and the number of doctors decreases slightly. [...] And that's just something where you get the feeling [...] that profit counts much more than satisfied patients. Because it just doesn't translate that much into numbers”. (Clinician Scientist, cluster: hybrid, male).

“The inhibiting factors are quite clearly the pressure, the economic pressure [...] That it is so tightly planned here. That in the end the clinical care has to be guaranteed and

everything else is, so to speak, secondary". (Junior Clinician Scientist, cluster: diagnostic, male).

In its economical dimension patient care is translated into numbers and these numbers are highly visible and countable – and even better countable than the ethically and professionally relevant patient satisfaction. The visibility and countability of these clinically related numbers help clinical practice gain visibility by creating a certain clinical need that has to be met by practitioners.

"Every clinic needs physicians who are predominantly clinically active and who take over the backbone of clinical care. Otherwise, i.e., only with scientists and people who are now striving for a university career, you cannot run a clinic today. Because we are all under economic pressure. And we also have to achieve certain economic goals. And you can't do that if you only have scientifically interested people in the clinic." (Clinic director, cluster: hybrid, female).

This need to meet economically driven numbers leads to the circumstance that the non-countable and non-visible research practice is pushed (even more) into the background.

We conclude from the empirical findings that the visibility of patient care is twofold: on the level of practitioners, visibility comes along with a valuation concerning its ethical dimension as a so-called "primary obligation" of being a doctor. Regarding its economic dimension, however, patient care reaches a super-visibility (Brighenti 2007), which is counteracting patient care in its ethical dimension. At the level of daily working practices, super-visibility means that it is considered more valuable to be present and to serve the acute and urgent clinical need that has arisen than to conduct research.

Comparing the relationship between visibility and evaluation in research and clinical practice, the following stands out: Clinical working practice is characterized by a very pronounced culture of presence. In comparison research practices sometimes also afford physical presence

for example when systematically executing and controlling laboratory experiments a. o. Nonetheless the variety of research practices at large is not generally carried out under the eyes of others and don't require the co-presence of others, especially patients, to the same extent as it is the case for clinical work and medical treatment. These divergent working practices and cultures feed back into the valuation of visibility and invisibility: Outside the medical field, making research visible by documenting, tracking and evaluating activities are seen as restriction to academic liberties and tends to be associated with annoying obligations of proof and evaluation, often associated with a lack of trust and undue desire of control. Conversely, the presence culture of the clinic effectuates that the visibility of medical work practices is associated with recognition and thus has positive connotations. In the light of these findings the clinician scientist program faces the question of how to increase visibility of research in the clinic?

How to make research more visible?

We find different practices in the interview data of how research is made visible by practitioners and how clinician scientists are valued for spending less time in the clinic than clinicians in order to practice research. The management level of the clinician scientist program recently instructed all clinic directors, who integrate clinician scientists in their clinical department, to implement a clinician scientist-tracing button in the time recording system of the university clinic that allows clinician scientists to register their actual time spent in research or in the lab next to their time spent in the clinic. This button is very much appreciated by all participants of the clinician scientist program and is widely used to make daily research visible for the university hospital management. Even though, research time cannot be traced adequately in each case, i.e. minute by minute, because research is not necessarily bound to fixed places or times such as patient care and treatment, clinician scientists endorse this tracing button as it

gives them legitimation for how they spend their time *officially*, which also helps them to protect their research time better from clinical duties.

“So, what has helped me extremely is the introduction of the research hours in the personalized assignment planning. The time record now shows exactly which research hours were taken and which were not. That creates transparency. And this means that those responsible are somewhat bound to say, “Okay, he really didn't get his research time,” because this is documented. And therefore, I really got the full research time now.” (CS, cluster: hybrid, male).

“However, this clinician scientist button is relatively new, and I know of colleagues who participated in the clinician scientist program three or four years ago [a time when the cs-button was not implemented yet] and they did a lot more clinical work. But the fact that it is now also reflected in the time recording system, that there is a much closer look at when research days are taken, how many hours are left in the time contingent, that makes it really easier to implement research” (Clinician Scientist, cluster: conservative, female).

The need to document research time is mainly caused by the lack of human resources in the clinic. Furthermore, a clinic director points out how staffing shortages causes occupation of research due to clinical practice.

“The framework conditions have to be set in such a way that there is actually close documentation of what the clinician scientists have spent their time on. Because, in the clinic and in patientcare, the staffing level is always too short. And then someone gets sick and then someone drops out and the clinic is too crowded with patients. And then our own senior physicians who work clinically always come and say, “But I'm missing an assistant here and now Ms. Müller and Mr. Meier [from the clinician scientist program] have to work clinically after all.” (Clinic management, cluster: conservative, female).

The documentation of research time taken has to be filled out by clinician scientists themselves. In some cases, interviewees mentioned that supervisors in the clinic (senior physicians) filled the time tracking for the clinician scientists. This leads to frustration on the individual level, because this practice is prone to obscure the factually performed division of labor between clinic and research and simultaneously counteracts the aim of that instrument, which was implemented to secure protected research time.

Analyzing the interview data, we find another (social) instrument to secure research time consisting in community building through rhetoric highlighting and justifying why clinician scientists are needed in university medicine. We asked clinic directors what the added value of clinician scientists for patient care is, despite the fact that the clinic seems to need (full-time) clinicians to fulfill the need of patient care and treatment.

„Interviewer: What would be the added value of clinician scientists for patient care? Perhaps in a broader sense as well?

Participant: Well, the added value is, of course, that clinician scientists also bring other aspects into patient care. So basically, you can say that I've never seen a good scientist, a good laboratory scientist, become a bad clinician. Because someone who works well and successfully in the laboratory has, let's say, a certain intellectual discipline. And also a talent to organize himself and his tasks. And that, of course, also benefits them in the clinic. And on the wards and also in clinical meetings, it is of course nice to have a clinician scientist, because they can also deepen the discussion or introduce new aspects. For example, in terms of pathophysiology, disease mechanisms, the effects of drugs, experimental therapies, etc., they can contribute more in-depth aspects that might otherwise be missing. I mean that is the purpose of university medicine. That you dig deeper. And to shed light on other aspects of patient care than is possible in a non-university hospital. In this respect, it is always an enrichment to have scientists here,

scientists on the wards or in the clinic in general.” (Senior physician, cluster: hybrid, female).

In contrast to non-university hospitals the purpose of university medicine is to do research and to “dig deeper” on medical problems. Clinician scientists contribute to this purpose by their double role of being a physician and researcher. It thus can be stated, that in order to make practices visible and articulable (Foucault 1972) and thus publicly negotiable, practitioners turn invisible practices into visible accounts. To be specific, laboratory research is made articulable tying it to relevant discourses such as research induced knowledge gain, broadening of diagnostic horizons and improvement of anamnesis and therapy in patient care; it is also rendered visible through measurable numbers documented and countable research hours spent in the lab as well as published and countable research papers. The clinician scientists and the supporting clinical management thereby secure to be able to justify the need for their partly invisible working practices based on measurable outcomes. In the present case of clinician scientists, the employees strive to document and trace their working practices in order to gain visibility as a means for recognition. They therefore gratefully value the time tracking system as an improvement of their working conditions.

Despite these practices to make research (more) visible in the clinic, an imbalance between research and clinic remains. We argue that this imbalance is problematic, not only for research but also for patient welfare: Because asymmetries in visibility between research and clinic tend to devalue the invisible and to overvalue the visible with significant consequences for sustainable medical innovation, they can endanger patient welfare in a long-term perspective and hence the improvement of health futures.

Asymmetries in Visibility and Valuation: The blurring boundaries of innovation

As we have seen, the interview-data provides multifaceted criticisms of asymmetries in visibilization and valuation practices in health economics, economization of the clinic and medical treatments. Moreover, the meaning and connotation of exploitation purposes such as innovation that run through clinical as well as through research work are critically scrutinized. Although innovation on the management level is mostly conceived in the sense of utilization/application and thus, broadly related to economic productivity, innovation is understood by clinician scientists comprehensively as any progress in the knowledge of a disease that has the potential to benefit patients and their best possible care, treatment, and even life extension. The understanding of innovation as renewal points in that direction.

"Innovation is something that has not yet be seen or something that brings renewal. In general, every publication is an innovation somehow, whether it's an innovation in knowledge or a technology that I either improve or bring to the table in a completely new way. That's why I would see a lot of things as innovations. If you restrict it in some way, then innovation is something that is either a substance or a technology that did not yet exist and that you can somehow make money from, if you define it so narrowly. But I would actually say that everything we publish is an innovation, because it brings new knowledge". (CS, cluster: hybrid, male).

Besides, several clinician scientists explain that innovation is not necessarily tied to economic benefits.

"I do think it has to have some use. The question is whether you always recognize the benefit immediately. Because there are many things where you only recognize the benefit afterwards. And just the fact that you have an insight, a new insight, even where the benefit is not quite clear yet, can of course still be an innovation." (CS, cluster: hybrid, male).

Furthermore, statements are dominated by the imagination that orientation towards profit is not a significant incentive or motivation for clinician scientists in their research. This shows the frequently discussed problem that with the question of utilization/application, a profit orientation and economic logic is introduced, which conflicts or is incompatible with the primary purpose of providing the best possible patient care.

"I think that the clinic system doesn't work if you put an economic pressure behind it and say you have to work in a profit-oriented way somehow, because patient care is just not profit-oriented." (CS, cluster: hybrid, male)

"For me personally, there is not such an economic incentive in this area. Rather, perhaps there is more of a clinical incentive that one establishes follow-up programs for patients or that it is ultimately obligatory paid by the health insurance or promoted that every patient gets a follow-up examination." (CS, cluster: hybrid, female)

Hence, the clinician scientist subordinate innovation to patient welfare in a holistic sense and not to the principle of economic efficiency. This understanding of innovation envisions how research could and according to clinician scientists should play an essential part in clinical practice in university medicine.

These frictions, disputes or disagreements around the conception of innovation reflect again that the unequally distributed visibility and its repercussions on the unequal value is problematic for at least two reasons: *First*, prioritizing patient care over research is detrimental to patient welfare in the long run. If medicine does not keep pace with the state-of-the-art research and new developments in the life sciences, it thus fails to use the technological and research achievements through medical clinical and translational research for patient care and undermines the goal of providing the best possible patient treatment (including anamnesis, diagnostics, selection of therapeutic approaches and their implementation). In the long run, losing touch with current research is therefore also negative for the sustainable care and

improvement of patient welfare (in a perspective of precautionary safeguarding of the most comprehensive possible public health).

Second, a dominance of clinic over research together with a permanent lack of human resources leads to cutbacks in patient care, which result in a mode of *acute medicine*: Long-term perspectives, such as the development of drugs and therapies, fall by the wayside in this system of acute medicine or, at best, are left to private pharmaceutical companies.

"In the end, it's like this, most of the time a publication comes along. And then you try to develop it piece by piece. And it's not as if one project is the same as founding a company. Rather, there are often many projects, many publications that all point in the same direction. And then, at some point, you say, "Okay, this is somehow a signaling pathway that you can address with the substance that you have investigated here and there." And that could actually be brought to fruition clinically on a larger scale". (CS, cluster: operative, male).

This acute mode of medicine provokes and prioritizes a privatization of health welfare instead of a public health (care) as part of the common good (Prainsack 2018; 2014; Dickenson 2016). The acute treatment of individuals and therefore the prioritization of clinic over research comes at the expense of providing continuously improved health care to the greatest number of people possible. We are hence facing a paradox, which only becomes accessible through the analysis of the regime of visibility, which we discuss in the following chapter.

Discussion: How visibility moderates' commodification

Visibility of research helps to overcome the pressure for commodification in the health care system, but at the same time drives economization even further. The first regime of visibility, we retrieved from the data, is bureaucratic and contains a general notion of objectification. This regime is ruled by a rigid counting and guiding system, which translates certain practices into quantifiable and measurable numbers (Vormbusch 2012). We find this notion of objectification

and quantification in research as well as in clinical practice: the need for counting publications, for counting patients, counting money spent for lab infrastructure, etc. results in a self-reinforcing dynamic: „[e]ffects of one’s visibility feedback from and to effects in one’s visibility” (Brighenti 2007, 331). The second regime of visibility, we retrieved from the data, is rhetorical and contains justifications. Again, according to Brighenti, visibility is the complex field where the visible and the articulable coexist and that the invisible is no less operative than the visible, but the invisible is without a theme (Brighenti 2007; 2017). Hence, this regime operates with articulable reasons, justifying why the invisible research practice is necessary in university medicine in addition to clinical practice and how it will or might benefit the medical system in the future: e.g. by providing and/or producing and/or enabling knowledge gain through research as an important valuation category for innovation as well as for translation. In translational work too, visibility is unevenly distributed. In (bio)medicine, research is mainly visible as an outcome (articles, patents, etc.) while clinical practice is mainly visible as a practice. The benefits of visibility however have a turning point: clinical practice – in its bureaucratic logic – occupy what Brighenti calls “super-visibility”. This super-visibility produces a state where patient treatment, which is counted via quantifiable numbers, becomes so highly visible that “patient welfare” in the holistic sense is no longer the basis for evaluation. In our study, we find that visibility of research is intimately related to commodification in health care and the rationality of visibility is paradoxically twofold: This intimate relation of commodification and visibility in health care fosters the hegemony of clinical acute patient care over medical research. Hence, regarding translation the crucial challenge consists in how to practice biomedical innovation, without getting captured by the pressures of economization. This tightrope walk reveals yet another frontline: It emerges along the question which regimes of purpose apply. Translational research and medicine are coined by the constant struggle over

how to balance the purposes of acute urgent patient care, further development and improvement of medical treatments and long-term assurance as well as preservation of patient welfare.

Conclusion: From innovation to translation: how to mediate, moderate, fraternize current clinical and research practices?

The terms translation and innovation are often used together, since translation is an essential moment of innovation and innovation in turn is an outcome of translation. In addition to their similarities, the two concepts differ in their dimensional characteristics. These characteristics are essential for illuminating the aspirations of clinician scientists and their role in university medicine.

Although, innovation is not necessarily bound to a certain field, e.g. economics, politics or science, the idea has spread that innovation is closely linked to utilization and thus to the principle of profitability. We find this understanding of innovation in our data as well. In university medicine, innovation addresses the gap between academic and clinical research and development and economic utilization. Based on our data, the innovation path can be described as follows: research – new knowledge – dissemination – commercialization. The clinician scientists' understanding of innovation, however, differs from this economic driven understanding. For clinician scientist's innovation overall addresses the improvement of medical treatments and therapies. The path of innovation thus goes from: research – new knowledge – dissemination – to optimizing medical treatment. Clinician scientists' clearly distance themselves from an economic understanding of innovation (see also Simons et al. 2019), although innovation can also have an economic or financial outcome such as start-up companies.

In light of these findings, we argue that the *concept of translation* compensates the overly dispersed conception and understanding of innovation tending either to dissolve into vacuity or to find its only anchor in commodification. Although economic utilization is one important

aspect of the concept of translation, translation is not necessarily bound to it. Bridging the gap between basic research, clinical research and medical treatment, translation is closely linked to an ethical dimension (Krueger et al. 2019), playing a crucial role for clinician scientists as physicians. *Prevention and health* are important elements of the translational justification narrative that allows clinician scientists and even full-time clinicians to switch to the clinic during acute situations and to prioritize clinic over research at that moment. With the concept of prevention, practitioners – this applies to all interviewed groups: clinician scientists, clinicians incl. clinic directors and research professors – can justify research with focus on possible future health concerns and thus direct their focus to the averting and avoidance of damage, whose emergence is perceived as probable. Compared to innovation, translation involves significant differences in the means-purpose relationship, which can be taken up by practitioners with the help of the prevention narrative and can thus be processed in an argumentative-legitimate manner. If translation is the more appropriate term to describe these actions in contrast to innovation, what happens to that translational justification narrative when (new) forms of visibility are placed on these practices, as we find in the case of research time tracking?

Translational work consists of the combination of research and clinical practice. Research needs protected time in clinical routine and therefore a minimum of visibility to be valuable. This valueability through visibility in our case is achieved through the time recording system providing proofs that can help for justification. However, over-regulation through counting and measuring performance generates a super-visibility – as illustrated by the example of patient care – which marks a crucial turning point: the intended goal of making things visible can no longer be pursued due to a shift in the logic invoked, which then hinders one to control the way and concepts in which the social image is handled and valued and thus, may force one to refrain from doing what one is actually supposed to do.

Correspondingly, research in the sense of contemporary research practice also needs a minimum of invisibility in order to be able to be practiced in self-directed, intellectually free, creative and innovation-promoting ways; i.e. in order not to be too much controlled by regulation. In a highly regulated world, such as that of clinical medicine, invisibility becomes a key moment for translational research and work. Invisibility operates in the sense of a protective space for those practicing researchers in that clinical context.

At this point the paradox becomes apparent: The concept of translation introduces research (as a non-countable and free practice) into the regime of economization. Our thesis at the beginning of the paper that a visible clinic is and (presumably) stays more powerful than invisible research finds its rationale here. It reflects the functionality of invisible research for research quality and thus translation. Translation must balance visibility and invisibility in research and clinical practice to enable qualitative novelty. The power of translation therefore lies in being able to maintain this balance and at the same time use it to optimize innovation processes – without having to subordinate itself entirely to the pressure of economization.

Our findings show that science policy concepts intrude the reality of science, not only in the intended way, but also by unfolding unintended side effects which change the values that are fundamental to the system. In light of these findings, our study complements existing discourses on the transformation of medicine and its consequences for society's health care (Dickenson 2016; Mackintosh and Koivusalo 2005; Mittra and Milne 2013; Prainsack 2018).

Literature

Anonymized/Pseudonymized: xxx 2015; xxx2016; xxx2019; xxx2021; xxx2022

- Abbott, A., 1988. *The System of Professions: An Essay on the Division of Expert Labor*. University of Chicago Press, Chicago.
- Berman, E.P., 2014. Not Just Neoliberalism: Economization in US Science and Technology Policy. *Science, Technology, & Human Values* 39, 397–431. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0162243913509123>
- Blümel, C., 2018. Translational research in the science policy debate: a comparative analysis of documents. *Science and Public Policy* 45, 24–35. <https://doi.org/10.1093/scipol/scx034>

- Blümel, C., Gauch, S., & Krüger, A. (2016). Organizing Translational Research: Report on the Establishment, Organization, and Evaluation of the Translational Research Process in leading US Organizations. DZHW-BIH-Report No. 2, online.
- Blümel, C., Gauch, S., Hendriks, B., Krüger, A., & Reinhart, M. 2015. In Search of Translational Research: Report on the Development and Current Understanding of a New Terminology in Medical Research and Practice. iFQ-BIH-Report January 2015.
https://www.bihealth.org/fileadmin/publikationen/dateien/iFQ-BIH-Report_2015_web.pdf
- Brighenti, A.M., 2017. The Social Life of Measures: Conceptualizing Measure–Value Environments. *Theory, Culture & Society* 35, 23–44. <https://doi.org/10/gfc8mx>
- Brighenti, A.M., 2010. Visibility in Social Theory and Social Research. Palgrave Macmillan UK, London. <https://doi.org/10.1057/9780230282056>
- Brighenti, A., 2007. Visibility: A Category for the Social Sciences. *Current Sociology* 55, 323–342. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0011392107076079fheBel>
- Butler, D., 2008. Translational research: Crossing the valley of death. *Nature* 453, 840–842.
- Çalışkan, K., Callon, M., 2010. Economization, part 2: a research programme for the study of markets. *Economy and Society* 39, 1–32. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03085140903424519>
- Çalışkan, K., Callon, M., 2009. Economization, part 1: shifting attention from the economy towards processes of economization. *Economy and Society* 38, 369–398.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/03085140903020580>
- Cambrosio, A., Keating, P., Mercier, S., Lewison, G., Mogoutov, A., 2006. Mapping the emergence and development of translational cancer research. *European Journal of Cancer* 42, 3140–3148. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejca.2006.07.020>
- Cavanaugh, T.A., 2018. Hippocrates’ oath and Asclepius’ snake: the birth of the medical profession. Oxford University Press, New York, NY.
- de Groot, E., Baggen, Y., Moolenaar, N., Stevens, D., van Tartwijk, J., Damoiseaux, R., Kluijtmans, M., 2021. Clinician-Scientists in-and-between Research and Practice: How Social Identity Shapes Brokerage. *Minerva* 59, 123–137. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11024-020-09420-7>
- Dickenson, D., 2016. Me medicine vs. we medicine: reclaiming biotechnology for the common good. Columbia University Press, New York.
- Dragun, D., Huber, N., Rösen-Wolff, A., Blomberg, R., 2019. Clinician Scientists. *Ärzte mit Kompetenz-Trias*. *Deutsches Ärzteblatt* 116, 2339–2340.
- Etzkowitz, H., Leydesdorff, L., 2000. The dynamics of innovation: from National Systems and “Mode 2” to a Triple Helix of university-industry-government relations. *Research Policy* 29, 109–123.
- Flink, T., Kaldewey, D., 2018. The new production of legitimacy: STI policy discourses beyond the contract metaphor. *Research Policy* 47, 14–22. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2017.09.008>
- Flink, Tim, Kaldewey, David, 2018. The Language of Science Policy in the Twenty-First Century: What Comes after Basic and Applied Research?, in: Kaldewey, D., Schauz, D. (Eds.), *Basic and Applied Research: The Language of Science Policy in the Twentieth Century*, European Conceptual History. Berghahn, New York Oxford.
- Foucault, M., 1972. *The Archaeology of Knowledge*. Pantheon Books.
- Hendriks, B., Schendzielorz, C., Heger, C., Reinhart, M. 2021. Kritische Bestandsaufnahme des BIH Charité (Junior) Clinician Scientist Programms: Untersuchungen einer integrierten Forschungs- und Facharztweiterbildung. Ergebnisse der Programmevaluation 2019/20.
<https://www.bihealth.org/en/translation/innovation-enabler/academy/clinician-scientist-program-evaluation>
- Honneth, A., 2010. Kampf um Anerkennung: zur moralischen Grammatik sozialer Konflikte; mit einem neuen Nachwort, 6. Aufl., [Nachdr.]. ed. Suhrkamp, Frankfurt am Main.

- Klein-Hitpaß, U., Scheller-Kreinsen, D., 2015. Policy trends and reforms in the German DRG-based hospital payment system. *Health Policy* 119, 252–257. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.healthpol.2015.01.006>
- Kleinman, D.L., Vallas, S.P., 2001. Science, Capitalism, and the Rise of the “Knowledge Worker”: The Changing Structure of Knowledge Production in the United States. *Theory and Society* 30, 451–492.
- Kraft, A., 2013. New Light Through an Old Window?: The “Translational Turn” in Biomedical Research: A Historical Perspective, in: Mittra, J., Milne, C.-P. (Eds.), *Translational Medicine. The Future of Therapy?* Pan Stanford Publishing, Singapore, pp. 19–55.
- Kraft, Alison, 2013. “New Light Through an Old Window?: The „Translational Turn“ in Biomedical Research: A Historical Perspective., in: Mittra, J., Milne, C.-P. (Eds.), *Translational Medicine: The Future of Therapy?* Jenny Stanford Publishing, Singapore, pp. 19–55.
- Krueger, A., Hendriks, B., Gauch, S., 2019. The multiple meanings of translational research in (bio)medical research. *History and Philosophy of the Life Science*, 41 (57).
- Kuhn, T.S., 1996. *The structure of scientific revolutions*, 3rd ed. ed. University of Chicago Press, Chicago, IL.
- Mackintosh, M., Koivusalo, M. (Eds.), 2005. *Commercialization of Health Care: Global and Local Dynamics and Policy Responses, Social Policy in a Development Context*. Palgrave Macmillan UK. <https://doi.org/10.1057/9780230523616>
- Martin, P., Brown, N., Kraft, A., 2008. From Bedside to Bench? Communities of Promise, Translational Research and the Making of Blood Stem Cells. *Science as Culture* 17, 29–41. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09505430701872921>
- Mayring, P., 2000. *Qualitative Content Analysis*. *Forum Qualitative Sozialforschung / Forum: Qualitative Social Research* 1.
- Mittra, J., Milne, C.-P. (Eds.), 2013. *Translational Medicine: The Future of Therapy?* Pan Stanford, Singapore.
- Owen, R., Macnaghten, P., Stilgoe, J., 2012. Responsible research and innovation: From science in society to science for society, with society. *Science and Public Policy* 39, 751–760. <https://doi.org/10.1093/scipol/scs093>
- Pettibone, K.G., Balshaw, D.M., Dilworth, C., Drew, C.H., Hall, J.E., Heacock, M., Latoni, A.R., McAllister, K.A., O, Fallon Liam R., Thompson, C., Walker, N.J., Wolfe, M.S., Wright, D.S., Collman, G.W., n.d. Expanding the Concept of Translational Research: Making a Place for Environmental Health Sciences. *Environmental Health Perspectives* 126, 074501. <https://doi.org/10.1289/EHP3657>
- Prainsack, B., 2018. The “We” in the “Me”: Solidarity and Health Care in the Era of Personalized Medicine. *Science, Technology, & Human Values* 43, 21–44. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0162243917736139>
- Prainsack, B., 2014. Personhood and solidarity: what kind of personalized medicine do we want? *Personalized Medicine* 11, 651–657. <https://doi.org/10.2217/pme.14.49>
- Reinhart, M. 2022 *Open Science as an Engine of Anxiety: How Scientists Promote and Defend the Visibility of Their Digital Selves, while Becoming Fatalistic about Academic Careers*, in: Brighenti, Andrea Mubi "The New Politics of Visibility", Intellect Books, S. 175-200.
- Reinhart, Martin. 2021. "Open Science as an Engine of Anxiety: How Scientists Promote and Defend the Visibility of Their Digital Selves, while Becoming Fatalistic about Academic Careers", in: Brighenti, Andrea Mubi "The New Politics of Visibility", Intellect Books. SocArXiv, <https://doi.org/10.31235/osf.io/2vr7j> (link).
- Reinhart, Martin, Anne K. Krüger, and Felicitas Hesselmann. 2019. “Nach der Bewertung ist vor der Bewertung – Sichtbarkeit und Emotionalität als verbindende Elemente von Bewertungsprozessen.” In (Be)Werten. Beiträge zur sozialen Konstruktion von Wertigkeit, edited by Stefan Nicolae, Martin Endreß, Oliver Berli, and Daniel Bischur, 125–45. *Soziologie des Wertens und Bewertens*. Wiesbaden: Springer VS. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-21763-1_6.

- Robinson, M.D., 2019. The market in mind: how financialization is shaping neuroscience, translational medicine, and innovation in biotechnology. The MIT Press, Cambridge, Massachusetts.
- Rose, N.S., 2007. Politics of life itself: biomedicine, power, and subjectivity in the twenty-first century, Information series. Princeton University Press, Princeton.
- Schumpeter, J., 2003. Theorie der wirtschaftlichen Entwicklung, in: Backhaus, J. (Ed.), Joseph Alois Schumpeter: Entrepreneurship, Style and Vision, The European Heritage in Economics and the Social Sciences. Springer US, Boston, MA, pp. 5–59. https://doi.org/10.1007/0-306-48082-4_2
- Van Hoyweghen, I., 2007. Risks in the Making: Travels in Life Insurance and Genetics. Amsterdam University Press, Amsterdam.
- Vignola-Gagné, E., 2014. Argumentative practices in science, technology and innovation policy: The case of clinician-scientists and translational research. Science and Public Policy 41, 94–106. <https://doi.org/10.1093/scipol/sct039>
- Vormbusch, U., 2012. Die Herrschaft der Zahlen: Zur Kalkulation des Sozialen in der kapitalistischen Moderne. Campus Verlag, Frankfurt.
- Voswinkel, S., 2001. Elemente einer Theorie von Anerkennung und Reputation, in: Anerkennung Und Reputation: Die Dramaturgie Industrieller Beziehungen: Mit Einer Fallstudie Zum “Bündnis Für Arbeit,” Analyse Und Forschung. UVK, Konstanz, pp. 23–156.
- Wilson-Kovacs, D.M., Hauskeller, C., 2012. The clinician-scientist: professional dynamics in clinical stem cell research. Sociol Health Illn 34, 497–512. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9566.2011.01389.x>
- Woolf, S.H., 2008. The Meaning of Translational Research and Why It Matters. Journal of American Medical Association 299, 211–213.

Appendix

TABLE 2: MEDICAL CLUSTER

Conservative	Operative & Interventional	Diagnostic	Hybrid
<i>Dermatology</i>	General and Abdominal Surgery	Human Genetics	Gastroenterology
<i>Endocrinology</i>	Anesthesiology	Neuropathology	Neonatology
<i>Hematology/Oncology</i>	Gynecology	Pathology	Nephrology
<i>Neurology</i>	Cardiovascular Surgery	Radiology	Pediatric Cardiology
<i>Pediatric Endocrinology</i>	Cardiology	(Laboratory Medicine)	Pediatric Respiratory Medicine
<i>Pediatric Hematology/Oncology</i>	Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery		Respiratory Medicine
<i>Pediatric Neurology</i>	Neurosurgery		Infectious Diseases

Psychiatry

Rheumatology

Radiotherapy

Ophthalmology

Orthopedics and Trauma

Surgery

Urology